

THE MAIN PROBLEMS OF DEVELOPING LISTENING COMPETENCE IN LEARNING ENGLISH AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Abstract. *This article aims to identify the main challenges faced by learners in developing listening competence in learning English as a foreign language. The paper begins by providing an overview of the importance of listening skills in language acquisition and the various factors that contribute to the complexity of listening comprehension. It then discusses the common problems encountered by learners and explores some possible solutions to them.*

Keywords: *foreign language, foreign language learning, language learning techniques, listening comprehension, oral speech, vocabulary, phonemic structure, grammatical structures, methodological techniques*

Introduction: English is widely recognized as the modern lingua franca. To communicate on a global scale, everyone must learn to speak and understand English. Speaking English facilitates communication with individuals from different parts of the world as it is the language of commerce and trade, science and technology. Knowing this language allows us to find information on almost any topic, because it is so widely used in international communication. All language skills—speaking, listening, reading, and writing—must be integrated in order to communicate. Of these, listening is the most crucial because it is the foundational skill for language learning. Since hearing is seen as a crucial aspect of language learning and instruction, it seems that the field of language teaching has focused heavily on it in recent years. There are, of course, challenges that make listening, since it involves more than just hearing words. While most students believe listening is the hardest ability to get better at, some teachers believe it is the easiest to teach. This paradox indicates that more research needs to be done on a few aspects of listening instruction.

Literature review: Many researchers, such as N.D. Galskova, N.I. Gez, S.V. Govorun, Z.R. Devterova, N.V. Elukhina, A.E. Mikhina, E.D. Sukhova, A.N. Shchukin, J. Field, J. Richards and others in their scientific works raise the problem of teaching listening as a need for integration and improving methodological techniques in the process of teaching foreign languages.

Solovova states listening as “a complex mental activity during which the listener must distinguish between intonation, phonemic structure, vocabulary and grammatical structures. For achieving a high level, it is necessary to master the perception and understanding of individual words, sentences, understanding the whole text and understanding the meaning”.

As N.L. Fedotova notes, listening has a number of additional functions: stimulating students' speech activity, ensuring management of the learning process, familiarizing students with new materials, developing skills and abilities for various types of speech activity, as well as the formation of self-control skills.

E.D. Sukhova gives the following classification of listening difficulties associated with:

- 1) Language form of the message;
- 2) Conditions of speech perception;
- 3) Individual characteristics of the speech source;

- 4) Perception of one or another type of speech;
- 5) Mastery sociolinguistic and sociocultural competences.

For Pogartseva, The basis of a language is grammar, designed to facilitate understanding of the structure of the language, in turn, vocabulary provides an understanding of the meaning, but for the initial listening speech perception requires the skill of listening to speech perception. In learning English, listening allows you to develop comprehension skills. The biggest problem of low speaking skills for students is a lack of practice. Most people can read and write fluently in English, but cannot carry on a conversation, it is impossible to achieve the desired result by studying only grammar and replenishing vocabulary. Typically, the listening skills of most people learning foreign languages are the least developed. However, they are recognized as necessary for successful communications at the present stage.

Analysis and results. Among the tasks that a teacher faces in connection with teaching foreign language, also includes the task of teaching listening and understanding foreign language speech. These skills are combined with the term “listening”. Most pupils and students study English for years, but despite this, many have difficulties when it comes to perception of oral foreign speech.

The first possible reason is that students try to understand every single word. Despite the fact that a person can calmly perceive speech in which large chunks of information are missing, speaking on a noisy street in their native language, many people cannot. It is easy to transfer this skill to a foreign language.

One of the solution methods of this problem is to show the student important words on which he should pay attention to when listening to a foreign speech. Another way is to give students one very simple task that they can complete, even if they do not understand the entire text. For example, define a name famous person or find something mentioned in the text repeatedly, such an exercise will help give confidence to a person, studying a foreign language and experiencing difficulties with performing listening tasks.

The second reason follows from the previous one and is that students lose the flow of the narrative of the entire text, trying to understand or remember the meaning of the previous word. A student tries to understand the meaning of a word from the context or correlate it with a similar word in the native language and because of this the meaning of the story is lost.

A solution to this problem can be to activate vocabulary on this topic before listening, which includes familiarization with lexical units that may cause difficulty, a short dialogue or discussion on the topic, and review of the vocabulary covered.

Lexical difficulties can cause problems in listening comprehension. They are that the student may have a weak vocabulary, and he may simply not know words that are important for understanding text. Lexical difficulties also include comprehension difficulties homonyms, paronyms, unusual combinations of words, numbers, the emergence idioms or realities.

As in the previous paragraph, here you need to work over knowledge of vocabulary and increase vocabulary.

The next sets of difficulties are phonetic difficulties. Islamova E.M. notes that at the phonetic level difficulties are associated with discrepancies in the spelling and pronunciation of words; mismatch in division text (sounding and graphic); assimilative phenomena in the speech stream. Thus, when listening, the student will not recognize the word that he knows. For example, for many Asians the words "led" and "red" will sound the same due to the phonetics of their native language. In this case, there is a clear connection with phonetics, accordingly, working on

pronunciation is a very important part for developing skills in understanding foreign speech in hearing.

The fifth difficulty is the problem of perceiving different accents. In the modern world, people have to deal not only with British and American accents, but also with Indian or French accents. To help a student in this situation, you just need to listen to how as many entries as possible in a foreign language and with different accents; for example, television or BBC World Service radio can focus on the pronunciation of sounds that are needed for understanding one accent or another.

Conclusion: In conclusion, teaching listening and understanding foreign language speech poses significant challenges for both teachers and students. These challenges stem from various factors such as the tendency to focus on individual words, the potential loss of narrative flow, lexical difficulties, phonetic discrepancies, and the diverse range of accents encountered in language learning. To address these challenges, it is essential to employ effective strategies. Encouraging students to focus on key words during listening exercises and providing simple tasks can enhance comprehension and boost confidence. Activating relevant vocabulary prior to listening tasks can aid in overcoming lexical obstacles, while emphasis on pronunciation and exposure to various accents through diverse listening materials can improve students' ability to comprehend different speech patterns.

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